

D1.8: Risk Management Plan (3)

WP1 – Project Management & Quality Assurance

Authors: George Karavias (KARAVIAS), Stergios Asteriou (KARAVIAS), George Voutsinos (KARAVIAS), Stylianos Silignakis (KARAVIAS)

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Other authors	Stergios Asteriou (KARAVIAS), George Voutsinos (KARAVIAS), Stylianos Silignakis (KARAVIAS)		
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1. Risk analysis and management

1.1. BEACON Risk Analysis and management

1.1.1. Risk identification

Based on the following risk categories, the risks faced so far and the potential new ones are presented below.

Risk Category	Risks faced
WP1 – Project Management & Quality assurance	RF1. Changes in the project team RF2. Delays in submission of project deliverables/ reports or requested input RF3. Lack of communication from Lighthouse Customers (LHCs) causing delays in deliverables RF4. Unavailability for monthly calls RF5. Alignment of the work done in various work packages RF6. Partners' reluctance to keep up with the deadlines RF7. COVID-19 pandemic situation
WP2 – Structural Agri value chain collaboration and co-evolution of business models and services	RF8. Assessment needs questionnaire was not effective and recipients had difficulties in responding RF9. Due to complexity of the blockchain, it was difficult to identify the users' requirements and needs RF10. LHCs experienced difficulties with understanding the BEACON functionalities only from mockups RF11. Different needs of the insurance companies; some insurance companies had requirements that are incompatible with the others RF12. The end-users have not understood the potential limitations of Earth Observation (EO) technology RF13. Lack of understanding of blockchain applications RF14. Failure to identify and clearly document the user requirements RF15. Users had difficulties in responding to the user requirements questionnaire RF16. Users concerned about data protection RF17. Difficulties to elicit the requirements from the end-users, either due to the users did not understand the questions or they had difficulties to explain the requirements (e.g. in terms of completeness and accuracy) RF18. Inadequate minimum viable product definition-validation-learning process
WP3 – Servitisation of Agri Business: Creating value by adding Earth(EO) data products and	RF19. Limitations in the acquisition and analysis of EO data, leaving gaps in claim-based insurance product RF20. Failure on the integration different components and fusion of different data types RF21. Transfer functions for biophysical parameters calculation were crop and region specific

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services	<p>RF22. Claim-based damage assessment failed to provide timely results</p> <p>RF23. The evaluation of the BEACON EO-meteorological products to estimate crop losses and hail damage show a limited quality and high level of uncertainty, with a general underestimation of losses</p> <p>RF24. Validation work was required and the addition of an “intelligence” layer, based on advanced machine learning techniques in order to reach higher accuracy</p> <p>RF25. SciHub new policy with regards to downloading archived Sentinel imageries</p>
WP4 – BEACON toolbox services & functions ecosystem: design and implementation	<p>RF26. Revision of the defined workflow</p> <p>RF27. Products (triggers, thresholds) were difficult to be defined</p> <p>RF28. Big number of issues have been reported</p> <p>RF29. Failure on integration with the blockchain</p> <p>RF30. Failure of underwriting the contracts due to gas limit restriction</p> <p>RF31. Overall architecture and ecosystem design</p> <p>RF32. Lack of understanding of how the blockchain and Smart contracts work</p> <p>RF33. Requests for additional services</p>
WP5 – Creating Business Experience & BEACON Accreditation path	<p>RF34. Data accessibility (meteorology, field visit and plot follow-up)</p> <p>RF35. Field work accessibility and tracking</p> <p>RF36. COVID-19 pandemic situation</p> <p>RF37. Due to the previous good weather conditions (2019-2020), farmers were reluctant to insure their fields this year (2021)</p> <p>RF38. Pilot activities had not been implemented according to the plan</p> <p>RF39. Insufficient data for the pilot implementation</p> <p>RF40. Delays of the pilot partners to provide the requested input</p> <p>RF41. Difficulties in collecting evaluation data with regards to costs</p> <p>RF42. Insurance companies’ reluctance to use the blockchain</p> <p>RF43. Definition of metrics to compare quality of BEACON in comparison to current alternatives/ existing workflows</p>
WP6 – BEACON Commercialisation Playbook and Growth Hacking	<p>RF44. Slow response of LHCs related to their inputs for BEACON</p> <p>RF45. Difficulties in developing trust between the BEACON solution and LHCs</p> <p>RF46. Poor interest of potential LHC</p> <p>RF47. No willingness of insurers to integrate the BEACON toolbox with their existing systems</p> <p>RF48. Concern about the data sharing</p> <p>RF49. Not clear roll-out plan for the Business Ambassadors</p>
WP7 – Dissemination, Communication and Diffusion of BEACON	<p>RF50. Low motivation of partners to actively engage on communication activities</p> <p>RF51. Inadequate reporting of partners for communication and dissemination activities</p> <p>RF52. Low performance in regards to the “Newsletter subscribers” and “Website page views” KPIs</p> <p>RF53. Failure to engage into the Agricultural Insurance (AgI) enablers significant stakeholders and interest groups</p> <p>RF54. Insufficient communication with the Advisory Board members due to AgIs enablers’ unavailability</p>

1.1.2. Risk Exposure

The table below presents the probability and impact of occurrence for the potential new risks using the following approach:

Probability of risk Occurrence:

- ⊗ High probability – (80% ≤ x ≤ 100%)
- ⊗ Medium – high probability – (60% ≤ x < 80%)
- ⊗ Medium – low probability – (30% ≤ x < 60%)
- ⊗ Low probability (0% < x < 30%)

Risk impact:

- ⊗ High – Risk that has the potential to greatly impact project schedule or performance;
- ⊗ Medium – Risk that has the potential to slightly impact project schedule or performance;
- ⊗ Low – Risk that has relatively little impact on schedule or performance.

		Probability of Occurrence			
		1= high	2= medium-high	3= medium-low	4= low
Risk impact	A= high	RF13, RF42	RF19, RF22, RF23, RF24, RF34, RF35, RF36, RF37, RF39, RF40, RF41, RF50, RF52, RF53, RF54	RF25, RF26, RF28, RF29, RF31, RF38, RF45, RF51	
	B= medium	RF7	RF9, RF12, RF14, RF15, RF17, RF18, RF30, RF32, RF33, RF44, RF46	RF3, RF5, RF10, RF47, RF48, RF49	RF21
	C= low				RF1, RF2, RF4, RF6, RF8, RF11, RF16, RF20, RF27, RF43

The colours represent the urgency of risk response planning and determine reporting levels.

1.1.3. Risk occurrence timeframe

The risks are classified based on the following timeframe:

Timeframe	Description
Near	Now- until one month
Mid	Next 2-6 months
Far	> 6 months

1.1.4. Risk response Plans

For each risk (faced or potential one), a risk response plan has been provided aiming to eliminate the risk, lower the probability of risk occurrence and depict the impact of the risk on the project’s objective.

FACED RISKS

Risk Event	Risk response
RF1. Changes in the project team	These challenges have been identified as soon as possible and the needed changes have been performed without minimizing the project’s impact. New partners included have equivalent (or higher) qualifications and experience.
RF2. Delays in the submission of project deliverables/ reports or requested input	In order to minimize the risk of delays, the consortium applied a strict project management procedure. If an indication of a possible delay arose, the respective WP leader and the coordinator discussed the implications. They worked on the development of an adequate strategy to counteract and minimize the negative impact of the delay.
RF3. Lack of commitment from LHCs causing delays in deliverables Change: From L-L to M-ML	Continuous iterations and communications with the LHC, providing also them with results and outcomes of the project activities. However, this lack of commitment had a medium/ low impact in the added-value of the final product, since the feedback was received from the project partners and the most active LHCs (not from all of them).
RF4. Unavailability for monthly calls	From the early stages of the project, the consortium agreed on a specific date for the every-month call. If a partner was not available to join the call, then the Project Manager was informed and they could arrange another call or read the minutes.
RF5. Alignment of the work done in various work packages	At points the work done in the various work packages lacked alignment and needed more attention and effort in order to bring everything together.
RF6. Partners’ reluctance to keep up with the deadlines	In order to minimise the risk of delays, the Project Manager requested the documents/ tasks needed from the

<p>Change: From M-ML to L-L</p>	<p>responsible partner through directly communication either via emails or skype. Reminders were sent before the due to date. If an indication of possible delay arose, the project manager requested a meeting through skype in order to identify the reason of this delay and assist the partner in any required manner.</p> <p>Despite the fact that there were cases of delays, due to the mitigation measures, these incidences were significantly reduced and had no great impact on the implementation of the project.</p>
<p>RF7. COVID-19 pandemic situation</p>	<p>The new era that was introduced due to the COVID-19 pandemic situation, had a medium risk on the project, since the consortium had already set guidelines on working in a daily and monthly basis remotely.</p>
<p>RF8. Assessment needs questionnaire was not effective and recipients had difficulties in responding</p> <p>Change: From M-MH to L-L</p>	<p>The needs assessment questionnaire was tested with a small group of recipients for comprehension and completeness. If this first small round revealed problems or deficiencies, corrective measures were applied before opening the process to a wider user group.</p> <p>The questionnaires have been revised and provided further information and details in order to be in a more understandable way to the targeted audience. Furthermore, calls have been organized and performed for further clarifications.</p>
<p>RF9. Due to complexity of the blockchain, it was difficult to identify the users' requirements and needs</p> <p>Change: From M-ML to M-MH</p>	<p>A separate session was dedicated to the identification and collection of users' requirements.</p> <p>However, the business workflow and the products of the insurance companies were not in line with the blockchain main purpose and the process of the collection of user requirements faced many difficulties.</p>
<p>RF10. LHCs experienced difficulties with understanding the BEACON functionalities only from mockups</p> <p>Change: From H-H to M-ML</p>	<p>The technical team provided live demonstrations during teleconferences and produced video demonstration.</p> <p>These approaches helped the end-users to better understand the logic of the BEACON solution, minimizing the risk of wrong collection of user requirements.</p>
<p>RF11. Different needs of the insurance companies; some insurance companies had requirements that are incompatible with the others</p>	<p>Although, there was noticed variability in the user requirements collected from different Agl companies, there was also a common concept, which was defined. All the specific requirements were also recorded.</p>
<p>RF12. The end-users have not understood the potential limitations of Earth Observation (EO) technology</p> <p>Change: From M-H to M-MH</p>	<p>Several direct communications were performed among the Agl companies involved in the project and the responsible team for the user requirements collection in order to thorough explain how the EO technology works and the potential of its application in the Agl context.</p> <p>All the end-users were familiar with the EO technology and</p>

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	during the communications that took place, it was easier to demonstrate to them its limitations.
RF13. Lack of understanding of blockchain applications	The end-users received detailed explanation (through presentations) of the advantages of using blockchain technology for smart contracts in AgI.
RF14. Failure to identify and clearly document the user requirements	To minimize this risk, the user requirements analysis was conducted in 3 stages (iterations). In the first stage, the basic understanding of the requirements was outlined. In the second stage, more detailed feedback from the end-users resulted in the first consolidated version of the user requirements which was further discussed and agreed with the end-users to produce the final version.
RF15. Users had difficulties in responding to the user requirements questionnaire	The end-users were provided with the support when responding to the questionnaire. Furthermore, during the direct calls with the end-users, a thorough interview was performed based on the questionnaires provided to clarify the uncertainties.
RF16. Users concerned about data protection	BEACON pays special attention to security and respects the privacy and confidentiality of the users' personal data, as described in the respective deliverables (Data Management Plan).
RF17. Difficulties to elicit the requirements from the end-users, either due to the users did not understand the questions or they had difficulties to explain the requirements (e.g. in terms of completeness and accuracy)	A user requirements analysis methodology was designed in order to avoid this risk. Three iterations were performed to ensure that the end-users would be involved in this process and all the misunderstandings and ambiguities would be clarified so as the questions to be understandable for the them.
RF18. Inadequate minimum viable product (MVP) definition-validation-learning process	A user requirements analysis was designed to estimate the priorities based on the users' business models. Close collaboration with several different AgI companies in the validation of MVP will ensure the process is adequate.
RF19. Limitations in the acquisition and analysis of EO data, leaving gaps in claim-based insurance product	The developed methodologies aim in synergistically applying optical and SAR data for both the qualitative and quantitative assessment of damage. This stands for hailstorm damage, as well as flood damage.
RF20. Failure on the integration different components and fusion of different data types Change: From M-H to L-L	Already a number of methodologies and automated workflows have been developed and implemented in OCTOPUSH operational system. BEACON's claim and index insurance schemes, fully exploit the following products and components: i.) Sentinel-2; ii.) Sentinel-1; iii.) two MODIS satellite products (the MOD16A2 ET and the GMOD09Q1 NDVI);

	<p>iv.) gridded meteorological data for the calculation of monthly SPI for drought monitoring and alerting;</p> <p>v.) an advanced coupling of a land surface model (Noah-MP) and a crop growth model (Gecros);</p> <p>vi.) seasonal climate predictions for the estimation of seasonal yield variations and anomalies;</p> <p>vii.) a machine learning model (support vector regression) for the estimation of drought damage (expected yield) at the end of the growing season;</p> <p>viii.) a machine learning model (support vector classifier) that takes into account a number of EO derived indices and biophysical parameters, as well as the crops' growing degree days for the classification of damage;</p> <p>Both the technical and the scientific teams consisted of experienced personnel able to solve any issue that might arise. Even if a technical issue might occurred, a backup plan always was available.</p>
<p>RF21. Transfer functions for biophysical parameters calculation were crop and region specific</p>	<p>Data for the calibration and validation of the transfer functions per crop and region have been provided by the LHC of BEACON. A detailed methodology for the calibration and validation and the results has been provided.</p>
<p>RF22. Claim-based damage assessment failed to provide timely results</p>	<p>The validation of methods for drought damage assessment led to the conclusion that NDVI-Anomaly cannot be used for yield prediction after drought damage. In the case of hail damage assessment, the phenology of the crop presents a significant limitation in the abstraction of a post-damage image from a pre-damage image. The DPI cannot be used during crop maturity with the tested indices. On the other hand, both simple and ML methods predicted hail and drought damage moderately to satisfactorily, especially when the provided datasets were uniform and every damage level was represented appropriately.</p>
<p>RF23. The evaluation of the BEACON EO-meteorological products to estimate crop losses and hail damage show a limited quality and high level of uncertainty, with a general underestimation of losses</p>	<p>To address the inaccuracies identified in the initially developed EO products for damage assessment the following methods were developed and tested against in-situ damage data:</p> <p>Hail Damage Assessment</p> <p>Two methodologies were tested and validated based on the Difference Percentage Index (DPI), which is calculated with the VI differencing technique, by the pre- and post-hazard Sentinel-2 or Sentinel-1 image:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. Standalone DPI methodology for hail damage assessment. II. Machine learning approach for hail damage assessment.

	<p>Drought Damage Assessment</p> <p>The Relative NDVI Anomaly (NDVI-A) is calculated by subtracting the MODIS NDVI values for a particular date range from the historical average for the same date range. The historical average is based on the MODIS NDVI values of the corresponding 8-day period from 2001 until present. Two methodologies that apply NDVI-A were developed and tested:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> III. An Indicator-Impact Calibration Equation Approach. IV. An Indicator-Impact Adjustment Machine Learning (ML) Approach.
<p>RF24. Validation work was required and the addition of an “intelligence” layer, based on advanced machine learning techniques in order to reach higher accuracy</p>	<p>For hail damage 1. a classification ML approach was developed to classify final parcel-based damaged and 2. a regression ML approach for the prediction of parcel-based damage percentage.</p> <p>For drought damage 1. a classification ML approach was developed to classify final damage on wheat and barley due to drought and 2. a regression ML approach was developed to predict final yield due to drought</p>
<p>RF25. SciHub new policy with regards to downloading archived Sentinel imageries</p>	<p>A complementary source was added to the workflow of the BEACON services, CREODIAS.</p>
<p>RF26. Revision of the defined workflow</p>	<p>Technical meetings have been arranged in order to identify possible deviations from the desired workflow. During these meetings, possible modifications have been discussed and based on their severity they will be prioritized. Furthermore, in order to minimize such a risk, a reporting system has been available to the end-users to report possible issues (Trello).</p>
<p>RF27. Products (triggers, thresholds) were difficult to be defined</p>	<p>Several technical meetings were held between the AgI providers actively involved into the project and the technical team in order to start creating the products. Furthermore, the involved parties tried to adapt this product closer to the AgI providers’ actual operational process.</p>
<p>RF28. Big number of issues have been reported</p>	<p>Regular meetings/ skype calls have been organized with the pilot users in order to frequently collect feedback and comments with regards to the toolbox’s operations. The feedback has been categorized, prioritized and reported on an issue tracking system and new releases of the toolbox has been done.</p>
<p>RF29. Failure on integration with the blockchain</p>	<p>Several calls have been performed in order to better facilitate this process and clearly understand how the integration should be performed and which actions should be done and by whom.</p>
<p>RF30. Failure of underwriting the</p>	<p>The gas limit was too low, resulting in “Out of gas” error</p>

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contracts due to gas limit restriction	when trying to process a large policy with a lot of parcels. The gas limit is a measure on how may computing steps can be performed in a single transaction. In a public blockchain, this value is typically limited to a number which ensures that all transactions can be processed and to prevent a DDOS attack (an attacker could run a transaction which takes a very long time to finish, thus blocking the whole blockchain). In the case of the BEACON project, the gas limit can be chosen arbitrarily, because the system is closed and protected from outside. Therefore, based on the parcels that each policy contains, an upper limit has been set and the gas limit has been calculated.
RF31. Overall architecture and ecosystem design	When different companies need to integrate their systems with each other it's always the question if this will work out well. We defined clear input agreements and deadlines amongst the development partners. Frequent calls and professional follow-up lead to an almost seamless integration.
RF32. Lack of understanding of how the blockchain and Smart contracts work	Several calls were held with the technical team in order to fully understand how the blockchain works and how it could be integrated with the BEACON platform. During the project, the process on the smart contracts was semi-automated since the full automation was not a desired option for the end-users.
RF33. Requests for additional services	During the project, and specifically, during the pilot implementation phase, there were some requests with regards to additional services. All of them were reported (and included into the respective deliverable) and investigated by the consortium if it was feasible to be incorporated into the current system. Some of them were included into the system during the project.
RF34. Data accessibility (meteorology, field visit and plot follow-up)	Data request for meteorological data was slowdown because of pandemic period. However, the pilot partners maintained continuous communication about pilot follow-up activities and find alternative sources in order to monitor the requested information. Lastly, an analysis was performed and described in the respective deliverable with regards to the products.
RF35. Field work accessibility and tracking	There were several governmental transportation restrictions because of the pandemic period between provinces. Field tracking of hazards was limited to farmer's claims reported to Agri companies. The monitoring process was performed through the toolbox and when the lockdowns ended and the companies had the resources the needed information was cross-checked.

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<p>quality of BEACON in comparison to current alternatives/ existing workflows</p>	<p>taken place between the responsible task leader and the pilot partners to collaboratively define the metrics, as well as explain and clarify any possible incomprehensiveness.</p>
<p>RF44. Slow response of LHCs related to their inputs for BEACON</p>	<p>Although all planned activities for the first semester have been successfully performed, mild alterations in the internally planning/calendar have been performed. The reasoning being the high workload of AgI personnel during this period, new contracts generation was undergoing, and a number of calamities caused a heavy workload for the AgI personnel. Following activities involving the LHC and new AgI members, took into consideration the timing and seasonality of their activities as well as included a time buffer in the activities' timeline.</p>
<p>RF45. Difficulties in developing trust between the BEACON solution and LHCs</p>	<p>Nurturing good relationships among BEACON partners and LHC actors was a key aim and objective of BEACON. The team from day one placed significant effort to fully involve and commit AgI-LHC members to the cause by involving them in a co-development process approach, as well as to gather detail requirements from their side that will address their pain points. Those actions in parallel to Confidentiality Agreements and Non-disclosure Agreements (NDA), signed among the involved entities, lead to the successfully establishment of a fruitful and transparent environment of trust among the entities.</p>
<p>RF46. Poor interest of potential LHCs</p>	<p>Although the AgI sector is heavily traditional, both in terms of operations as well as in terms of innovation adoption, during the early months of the project the AgI companies were very open to attend and hear about BEACON activities and expected outcomes. Furthermore, to ease the communication and approach of AgI actors, the BEACON Business team applied a twofold approach, combining the circulation of communication material prior and after the B2B meetings.</p>
<p>RF47. No willingness of insurers to integrate the BEACON toolbox with their existing systems</p>	<p>Despite the fact that there was no willingness of insurers to exploit the full utilization of this component, there was an interest from their side with regards to the services and how they can be better adjusted into their specific area and business needs, even after the end of the project.</p>
<p>RF48. Concern about the data sharing</p>	<p>AgI companies provided input, contained to an extent data of their and their client's interest. Since this input was very important for the development of BEACON Toolbox, BEACON Business & Development team prepared and signed BEACON Confidentiality Agreement with AgI companies to secure all uncertainties regarding the data sharing.</p>

<p>RF49. Not clear roll-out plan for the Business Ambassadors</p>	<p>Firstly, the consortium has defined the profile for future BEACON Ambassadors and the BEACON LHCs acted as Ambassadors of the BEACON toolbox during the commercialization phase. Within BEACON, we defined Ambassadors as assigned individuals – staff of Agri companies – BEACON LHCs that were directly involved into project whether via pilot implementation activities or business development activities. Such was based on the novel marketing theories, focusing on the first users (here - Lighthouse Customers) that can best communicate the essence of the BEACON Toolbox as a solution. Namely, this strategic approach was a unique opportunity to foster a brand positioning of the project and at the same time, the toolbox, using the BEACON LHCs to spread the BEACON experience. As BEACON Toolbox represents the solution that generates the value through the credibility and relevance of its user, as well as through the co-creation with them, creating the brand in this way has become an imperative.</p> <p>After the definition of BEACON Ambassador’s profile, the next step was to empower them to act as a “inspiration” for potential future customers. Here, some moves were already made naturally by our LHCs (Triglav, AgroSeguro, Karavias, Agrisk) as they present the authentic “word-of-mouth marketing”, bringing the concrete results to BEACON business development through direct promotion of the solution and easier organization of B2B meetings with potential new customers.</p>
<p>RF50. Low motivation of partners to actively engage on communication activities</p>	<p>Partners’ obligations were distributed early in the project. Regular and extraordinary reminders were also sent when needed, while details guidelines were given during the consortium meetings and through personalised recommendations.</p>
<p>RF51. Inadequate reporting of partners for communication and dissemination activities</p>	<p>Periodic reporting was managed by the WP leader using a relevant calendar. Partners were alerted in advance to use either the dedicated online platform of reporting or the word document templated stored in the DROPBOX account.</p>
<p>RF52. Low performance in regards to the “Newsletter subscribers” and “Website page views” KPIs</p>	<p>Due to the initial misspecification of the target values of the particular KPIs, dozens of campaigns were made in LinkedIn groups to enlarge the pool of the newsletter subscribers. Regarding the website page views it was decided to intensify the project’s posts, as well as their sharing in all social media platforms used by the project’s team personal accounts.</p>
<p>RF53. Failure to engage into the</p>	<p>Continuous research was on the WP’s leader agenda to</p>

2. Conclusions

The present deliverable is the final version of the Risk Management Plan, addressing and showcasing all the identified and faced risks along with the mitigation measures that the consortium took in order to minimise their impact.

